

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract: The issue of education of children with disabilities is becoming one of the most pressing issues today. At present, in order to carry out education in a special or general education system according to the level of development, opportunities, features and abilities of children in need of special assistance in the Republic, the inclusive education system is being implemented. Inclusive education culture! —In accordance with the Salamanca declaration, the Khar is viewed as a proof, supporting and approving reform of the characteristics of a reader. Its objectives are to prevent social segregation caused by differences in gender, race, culture, social nationality, religion, individual opportunity and ability. However, it turned out to be unsuitable for conception universal use. According to world, inclusion in schools is often regarded as the education of disabled people in secondary schools along with their peers (Judi Kugel'mas) however, knowledge and knowledge of the essence of inclusive education is not yet sufficient in the society. The terms "inclusive" and "integrated" are often used in the same meaning. But despite the fact that in philosophy there is a huge difference between these concepts.

Key words: Education, children, disabilities, special education, general education, inclusive education, social segregation, school, disabled people,

integrated, gender, general education institutions.

Sharqning mashxur allomalari Ibn Sino, Imom Buxoriy, Abu Nasr Farobiy, Alisher Navoiy, Abdulla Avloniylarning tarbiyaning maqsadlari har bir bola shaxsining rivojlanishiga ta'limning ta'siri tug'risidagi qarashlari inklyuziv talim rivojlanishining metodologik bazasi xisoblanadi. Juda uzoq vaqt davomida maxsus yordamga muhtoj bolalarni umumta'lim muassasalariga nisbatan maxsus segregatsion ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim tarbiya berish samarali deb hisoblanib kelindi. 1970-1980 yillarga kelib jahon miqyosida insonparvarlik va kamsitishlarga yo'l qo'ymaslik g'oyasining ilgari surilishi maxsus ehtiyojli bolalarga e'tiborning yanada yaxshilanishiga olib keldi.

Mazkur maqolani tahlil qilish jarayonida ilmiy bilishning mantiqiylik, tarixiylik, izchillik va obyektivlik usullaridan keng foydalanildi. Inklyuziv ta'limda nogiron bolalarni o'qitish va tarbiyalash muammolari haqida qisqacha tahlil olib borildi. Крыжановская Л.М. "Психологическая коррекция в условиях инклюзивного образования. Пособие для психологов и педагогов" nomli kitobi mantiqiy tahlil sifatida olindi.

Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida quyidagi maqsad va vazifalarning hal etilishi talab etiladi: - ta'lim muassasasida imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar va usmirlarning ta'lim olishlari uchun zaruriy psixologik-pedagogik, korreksion sharoitlarni yaratish, ularning imkoniyatiga yunaltirilgan umumta'lim dasturlari va korreksion ishlarni amalga oshirish orqali ruxiy rivojlanishi, ijtimoiy moslashtirishni amalga oshirish; - o'quvchilarning ta'limdagi tenglik xuquqini kafolatlash; - jamiyatning va oilaning faol ishtirokida nogiron va saglom bolalarning extiëjlarini qondirish, ijtimoiy xaëtga erta moslashtirish; - imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar va usmirlarni oilalardan ajramagan xolda yashash xuquqini ruëbga chiqarish; - jamiyatda imkoniyatti cheklangan bolalar va usmirlarga nisbatan dustona va mexr-muxabbatli munosabatni shakllantirishdir. Inklyuziv ta'limning muammolari. Ko'plab davlatlarda inklyuziv ta'limni joriy etish bo'yicha davlat normativ xujjatlarida qayd qilinmaganligi; Nogiron bolalarga nisbattan salbiy munosabat;

Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning hamjamiyatda ko‘rinmaslik muammosi; Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning maktabda ko‘rinmaslik muammosi; Moddiy mablag‘ muammolari; Ta'lim muassasalarini moslashtirish; Sinfda o‘quvchilar sonining ko‘pligi; Kambag‘allik; Jinsiy tafovutlarga qarab kamsitish; Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning boshqalarga qaramligi; Favqulodda vaziyatlar , mojarolar, qochoqlar; Kadrlar masalasidagi muammolar. Haqli savol tug‘iladi, nima uchun imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarni inklyuziv ta'lim tizimiga jalb etish kerak? Yuqorida keltirilgan dalillarni hal etib inklyuziv ta'lim tizimiga o‘tishga qanday zaruriyat bor? Darhaqiqat, bu ta'lim tizimi oldidagi muammolarni hal etish oson kechmaydi. Ammo bu ta'lim tizimining nafli jixati juda ko‘p ular sirasiga qo‘yidagilar kiradi:) Inklyuziv ta'lim qashshoqlik iskanjasidan qutilishga imkon beradi;) Inklyuziv ta'lim barcha uchun ta'lim sifatini yaxshilaydi;) Kamsitishlarni oldini oladi;) Inklyuziv ta'lim yanada inklyuzivlikka olib keladi.1

Inklyuziv ta'limning prinsiplari: 1. Insonning qadr qimmati, uning qobiliyati va yutug‘iga bog‘liq emas. 2. Har bir inson o‘ylash va xis qilish qobiliyatiga ega. 3. Har bir kishi eshitish va muloqot qilish qobiliyatiga ega. 4. Har bir kishi bir\biriga muxtoj. 5. Shaxsning to‘liq va haqiqiy ta'lim olishi faqat real hamkorlikda amalga oshadi. 6. Hamma kishilar o‘z tengdoshlarini qo‘llab quvvatlashga muxtoj. 7. Hamma ta'lim oluvchilarni yutuqga erishishiga ularning nimadir qila olmasligi emas , balki nimanidir qila olishidir. 8. Hamkorlik qilish kishi haetini har tomonlama ko‘chaytiradi. Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimi qo‘yidagi ta'lim muassasalarni o‘z ichiga oladi; maktabgacha umuta'lim, umu o‘rta ta'lim, o‘rta maxsus kasb-xunar va oliy ta'lim. Bu ta'lim muassasalarning maqsadi bolalarning ta'lim olishi va kasb-xunarga tayèrlashda ularning o‘rtasidagi to‘siqlikni bartaraf etib ochiq ta'lim muxitini yaratishdan iborat. Umumta'lim maktablarda alohida dastur va darsliklardan foydalanish imkoniyati bo‘lmaydi. Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimi integratsiyalashgan ta'lim tizimidan uzinig mazmun – moxiyati, maqsadi, vazifalari va xarakat dasturi bilan farqlanadi. Bolaning tarbiya va o‘quv

faoliyatida orqada qolishi psixik funksiyalarni o'zlashtirmaganligi natijasidir. Masalan, bolaning kiyim kiyishida ketma-ketlikning buzilishi uning xotirasi zaifligidan emas, balki ushbu jarayonni amalga oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan malakalarni egallamaganligi tufayli ro'y beradi. Bunday psixik muammoni psixoreksiyalash usullari bilan birga bolaga kiyimlarni to'g'ri ketmaketlikda kiyish tasvirlangan rasmlar taqdim etilishi mumkin. L.S.Vigotskiy ijtimoiy muhit sog'ligi imkoniyatlari cheklangan bolalar uchun birinchi darajali ahamiyatga egadir, degan g'oyani ilgari suradi. 2 Xuddi shuningdek, u imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning rivojlanishini ildizi yomon o'simlikka o'xshatadi. «Uning ingichkagina ildizlari oziqlantiruvchi tuproqning qatlamlari va shakliga mos kelmaydi. Ular o'zo'zicha tuproqning oziqa beruvchi qatlamlariga yetib borolmay, quruq va zaharli qatlama kirib qoladi. Bunday o'simlik muvofiq sharoitlarda gullashi mumkin edi, biroq odatdagi sharoitda taraqqiyotning cho'qqisiga yetmasdan, bujmayib so'lib qoldi», deydi. 3 Binobarin, ta'lim-tarbiya tizimini har bir millat va elatning o'ziga xos tomonlari, milliy an'analari, urf-odatlari, davlatning maqsad-vazifalari hamda tarbiyalanuvchilarning ruhiy va jismoniy rivojlanishidagi xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda ishlab chiqish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarda kattalar bolaning rayiga, mustaqil bo'lishiga qarshi turmasdan, mumkin qadar istagi, intilishiga yordam bersalar, uning shaxsini shakllantirish jarayonidagi qiyinchiliklar o'z-o'zidan barham topadi. Imkoniyati cheklangan bolada o'jarlik, qaysarlik, itoatsizlik xususiyatlari paydo bo'lishi bu kattalarning haddan tashqari paypaslaganliklari oqibatida vujudga keladi. Psixolog olimi L.M.Krijanovskaya imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida ta'lim-tarbiya berishda psixologik korreksiyalash metodlari orqali tarbiyalash yo'llarini keng yoritib bergan. Uning fikricha, inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida ta'lim-tarbiya ishlarining samarali bo'lishi, yaxshi yutuqlarga erishishda maktab psixologi, pedagog, tarbiyachi va ota-onalar hamkorligi uzviy bog'langan bo'lishi lozim.4 Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida jahon miqyosida amaliyotga joriy qilish borasida bugungi kunga

qadar ham juda ko'plab muammolar va to'siqlar mavjud. Ular jumlasiga quyidagilar kiradi: Salbiy munosabat; Hamjamiyatda ko'rinmaslik; Moddiy mablag' muammolari; Jismoniy moslashtirish; Sinfdagi o'quvchilar soni; Qaramlik; Jinsiy belgilarga qarab kamsitish; Favqulodda vaziyatlar, mojarolar va qochoqlar. Salbiy munosabat-maxsus ehtiyojli bolalarning umumta'lim muassasalari tizimida ta'lim tarbiya olishlari uchun eng katta to'siq bo'lsa kerak. Salbiy munosabat muammosining mazmuni shundaki, ota-onalar, hamjamiyat a'zolari, o'qituvchilar, umumta'lim muassasalari hodimlari, boshqaruv organlaridagi hatto maxsus ehtiyojli bolalarning o'zlaridagi umumta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim tarbiya olishlariga nisbatan qashiliklari va buni istamasliklaridir. Bunga sabab nogironlarga nisbatan insonlardagi noto'g'ri fikr, ular to'g'risida ma'lumotlarning yetishmasligi, nogiron bolalarning chegaralangan muhitda o'sganligi va boshqalardir. Hamjamiyatda ko'rinmaslik muammosining mazmuni shundaki, ko'pincha ko'plab maxsus ehtiyojli bolalar ota-onalar tomonidan qattiq bekitiladi. Ularni uyga qamab hyech kimga ko'rsatmaydilar, ro'yxatga olish jarayonida nogiron bolasi to'g'risida hyech bir ma'lumot berilmaydi. Natijada ko'plab nogiron bolalar hamjamiyatda ishtirok etishdan mahrum bo'ladilar. Ular to'g'risida hyech bir ma'lumotni bo'lmasligi ta'lim-tarbiya muassasalariga qatnamasliklariga olib keladi. Inklyuziv ta'limni amaliyotga joriy etish ustida olib borilgan tajribalardan shu narsa o'z isbotini topdiki, har qanday imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarni nuqsonini ilk yoshdan o'z vaqtida aniqlab mutaxassislarga murojaat qilinsa va maktabga tayyorgarlik ishi o'z vaqtida olibib borilsa abatta ko'zlangan maqsadga erishish mumkin. Ya'ni inklyuziv ta'limning samarasi yuqori darajada bo'ladi.

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